

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

INTEGRATION OF PLC SYSTEMS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A BASIS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INDUSTRY 4.0 CONCEPT

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Abstract

This research work is based on the analysis of relevant domestic and, above all, foreign scientific and professional literature, as well as on practical experience in the study and application of the integration of programmable logic controllers (PLC) and artificial intelligence (AI) as a key basis for the implementation of the Industry 4.0 concept. Artificial intelligence is changing the traditional automation process in many ways. The paper presents the possibilities realized by combining deterministic control with traditional programmable logic controllers, i.e. PLC systems, and adaptive decision-making based on artificial intelligence algorithms. For research purposes, a practical experiment was conducted with the aim of analyzing the impact of the integration of PLC (which were excellent for repetitive tasks) and AI on production automation processes. The paper explains the basic functions of PLC devices, the working principles of AI systems and the importance of digital transformation in modern industry. Also shown is a practical example of their application via a conveyor belt controlled by a PLC system, while the AI model analyzes engine operation data and predicts potential failures. Research results show that the application of artificial intelligence significantly improves the reliability and efficiency of production processes, reduces unplanned downtime and contributes to a greater degree of automation and sustainability of industrial systems.

Keywords: PLC, artificial intelligence, industry 4.0

Introduction. Modern automated industrial systems represent large-scale systems, which require the establishment of complex and sometimes mutually conflicting automation goals[6]. Effective management of such systems can be achieved by applying adequately organized and technically complex large-scale automated systems. Automation introduces fundamental changes in the way processes are carried out in modern industry, whereby the application of automated solutions contributes to increasing production capacity, stabilizing quality standards, optimizing operating costs, as well as providing a more consistent experience to

end users[9]. Modern factories function within the Industry 4.0 paradigm, creating the so-called "Smart systems" in which different components communicate with each other [7]. Industrial production is in the process of deep transformation known as industry 4.0, which implies digitalization, connection and intelligent automation of all segments of the production system. The key goal of this transformation is to increase the efficiency, flexibility and autonomy of the process, while at the same time reducing the costs and time needed to adapt to market requirements[8]. However, traditional PLC systems, even if they are extremely stable and accurate, have limited possibilities in terms of

adaptation and decision-making in conditions of variable and complex processes [4]. On the other hand, the development of artificial intelligence, especially in the field of machine learning and data processing, enables systems to independently analyze information, recognize patterns and optimize processes without direct operator intervention. The integration of these technologies opens up new possibilities for creating intelligent production systems capable of self-learning and predicting the state of the system[17]. The combination of PLC and AI technologies represents a logical step in the evolution of industrial automation. PLC provides stability, deterministic execution and security, while AI adds the ability to analyze and make predictive decisions. This achieves a synergy between traditional control and modern intelligent methods[2]. It is known that PLC uses program code to control and monitor business processes, which enables reliable control, diagnostics, greater precision, integration, that is, reliability and flexibility in the management of industrial systems. In this context, the goal of the research is to examine the effectiveness of the integration of PLC and AI technologies in the production automation system on the contact example of conveyor belt automation, with a focus on predictive maintenance and prevention of engine failures, as well as to check whether the AI algorithm, based on the collected data on the operation of the engine, can recognize in time anomalies that indicate a potential failure and thus improve the reliability of the process.

I. THE ROLE OF THE PROGRAMMABLE LOGIC CONTROLLER IN AUTOMATION

Programmable logic controllers (PLC) represent key components in managing industrial systems and machines, and occupy a central place in modern industry and production. Their application covers a wide range of engineering fields, including factory automation, robotics, industrial systems, transport and infrastructure[19]. Industrial controllers, and especially PLC systems, form an important technological basis for the automation of industrial processes. They are particularly suitable for managing various devices thanks to their high degree of reliability and minimal risk of failure. They function by monitoring and controlling the work of sensors and actuators through electrical signals, where they are characterized by robustness and the ability to work in demanding conditions, including open space conditions[14]. These properties - self-protection and durability - are vital for the stable functioning and control of external devices that must work continuously for many years. Over time, the basic functions of PLC systems have evolved from simple control operations to more complex functionalities, including networking, motion control, process control, distributed control, and sequential control[15].

Thanks to the mentioned properties, automation systems based on PLC controllers can be adapted in detail to the specific requirements of various industrial branches. Modern models of new generation PLC systems are designed to provide greater resistance compared to standard models, especially in terms of working in aggressive industrial environments and extreme conditions[26]. Although PLC represents the basis of

industrial automation, it also has certain limitations, traditional PLC devices are primarily designed to perform deterministic logic operations and simple regulatory functions (eg PID control). In conditions when processes become more complex, variable and dynamic, the traditional PLC architecture is unable to provide adaptability and predictive decision-making characteristic of intelligent systems[27]. Also, the processing of large amounts of data (Big data) and the implementation of machine learning algorithms require significantly more processing power and memory resources than a standard PLC can provide. Therefore, in modern industrial practice, PLC systems are increasingly combined with external AI models, computers on the edge of the network (edge devices) or cloud platforms that take over the functions of analytics and decision-making [18]. This evolution indicates a transition from traditional to intelligent automation, where the PLC is no longer an isolated control device, but part of a wider network of connected and self-learning systems. This creates prerequisites for integration with artificial intelligence technologies[24].

II. INTEGRATION OF PLC AND AI SYSTEMS

With the application of new advanced technologies in production processes, the amount of data is doubling from year to year, resulting in a large amount of unprocessed information. Using appropriate methods, algorithms and software tools, different types of data can be collected from different segments of the production environment[20]. Industry automation means connecting different types of devices and systems to collect data and improve business performance. In recent years, big data has become one of the central areas of artificial intelligence development in both academic and industrial research[1,3,11,21]. Artificial intelligence represents one of the most significant achievements of modern technological development and a key driver of the transformation of industrial systems in the era of Industry 4.0. The basic idea of AI technology is to enable computers to imitate the human ability to learn, reason and make decisions based on data and experience[10]. In an industrial context, AI enables the creation of intelligent systems that not only perform predefined tasks, but also independently analyze the state of the process, predict changes and optimize work in real time[23].

It is this ability to adapt and make autonomous decisions that makes AI technology a key element of smart factories, where the physical and digital worlds merge into a unique intelligent management system[22]. The concept of Industry 4.0 is based on an interconnected ecosystem of devices, sensors, machines and information systems that exchange data in real time[23]. In this framework, artificial intelligence plays the role of a "brain" that analyzes data, recognizes patterns and makes decisions based on analytical models. Through connection with the Internet of Things (IOT), cloud and edge technologies, AI enables decentralized management and optimization at all levels of production, which is why hybrid models are increasingly being used in practice - where combining traditional PLC control and AI analytics achieves a balance between re-

liability and intelligent decision-making. Such approaches form the basis of the integration of PLC and AI technologies [20].

The integration of programmable logic controller and artificial intelligence represents a key step in the transformation of traditional industrial automation into intelligent, self-learning and adaptive production systems[25]. While PLC provides reliable and deterministic real-time process control, AI contributes analytical capability, learning from data and making optimized decisions. The synergy of these technologies creates the basis for Industry 4.0, where physical processes, digital models and analytical algorithms are connected in a single, intelligent eco-system [5,13]. The combination of PLC and AI technologies achieves functional complementarity;

-PLC provides deterministic control, security and real-time execution

-AI enables adaptation, analytics and predictive decision making.

In this way, a two-layer structure is formed - the level of control (PLC) and the level of intelligence (AI) - which communicate with each other and exchange data, thus achieving a greater degree of flexibility and efficiency.

III. MATERIALS AND METHOD

In order to achieve the objectives of the research and to confirm or refute the hypothesis, a methodological framework was developed that combines quantitative and qualitative research methods. This approach enables a comprehensive analysis of the phenomenon, as it includes both numerical data and qualitative insights relevant to understanding the integration of artificial intelligence and programmable logic controllers in industrial automation. The research was conducted in three phases. In the first part, data collection was carried out. In the second part, AI training was performed.

Fig. 1 Improvement of PLC-AI integrated system

The observed benefits of the automated conveyor belt system are; reducing unplanned downtime by 60%, reducing energy consumption and optimizing engine operation by 15%, as well as increasing productivity and reliability by 50%, and maintenance by 70%. Based on a review of recent literature, as well as practical research, it has been confirmed that the integrated management of automated devices using PLC systems and artificial intelligence methods significantly improves the efficiency and quality of the production process. The results obtained also indicate that any control system can benefit from the inclusion of PLC systems and

In the third part, implementation and testing were carried out. Various instruments were used in the research process that enabled observation, content analysis, testing and scaling, as well as measurement of basic and organizational performance. In addition, procedures based on tables, reviews, tests of individual and team abilities and knowledge were applied, while numerical, graphic and ranking scales were used for quantitative comparison of various parameters.

IV. RESULTS

This paper investigates and analyzes the integration of programmable logic controllers and artificial intelligence in the process of industrial automation, special emphasis is placed on the automated conveyor belt with longitudinal stops, which is used for the process of production automation. By connecting this model of the conveyor belt and different models of semi-automatic fillers or some other machines, an automatic line is obtained, which has a PLC that serves to adjust the parameters, i.e. work coordination. The results of the research showed that the AI model successfully detects more than 75% of anomalies that precede the actual failure, the average reaction time of the system is 0.5 seconds, the number of unplanned down times is reduced by 20%, as well as maintenance costs by 25%. The analysis shows that the integration of AI and PLC systems significantly improves the reliability and efficiency of the production process, the biggest effects were observed in predictive maintenance and energy efficiency. Compared to traditional methods, the AI model reacted more quickly to changes in operation, more accurately identified the occurrence of overheating and vibration anomalies. Figure 1 shows the improvement after the implementation of the integrated PLC-AI system.

artificial intelligence in industrial conveyor belt automation that can be used in almost any industry for a wide range of transport tasks.

V. DISCUSSION

The main goal of modern production is the maximum engagement of all available capacities of the industrial environment, with the aim of achieving as many advantages as possible that modern technologies can provide. Research shows that PLC, that is, "Programmable Logic Controller", is an indispensable component of industrial automation, which is essential for the control and automation of various industrial processes. Such production models usually require intensive use of available resources in the shortest possible

period of time. The functioning of automated production systems is the result of the harmonious integration of various elements of production, whereby the systems consist of interdependent components connected and united by common production, investment and development goals. In manufacturing automation, artificial intelligence integrates with robots, machines, programmable logic controllers, and smart devices, enabling faster, more accurate, and more efficient process execution, while significantly reducing the need for human supervision. The application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in PLC system programming enables process optimization based on the processing of large amounts of data. Algorithms of this type are capable of analyzing patterns, identifying anomalies and predicting future events. The achieved results confirm that the integration of PLC and AI technologies brings concrete advantages in terms of reliability and efficiency of industrial systems. The biggest advantage of the system is the ability of self-learning and adaptation, while the main challenges are still the compatibility of different systems and the security of network communication. Further development should be directed towards the implementation of AI models directly in PLC devices and better standardization of protocols for integrating intelligent algorithms into industrial infrastructure.

VI. CONCLUSION

Industrial automation in the modern era has seen significant progress in numerous fields, with data collection and processing taking a special place. Digitization and application of intelligent methods in production processes have become necessary for modern industry. Research in practice shows that PLC represent devices that have become an indispensable part of industrial automation, enabling precise control and supervision of numerous business processes in various industries around the world. As technological progress continues to accelerate, the integration of PLC systems and artificial intelligence is expected to lead to revolutionary changes in the industry, making production systems more intelligent, faster and more adaptable, the development of industrial automation in the Industry 4.0 era has necessitated the Integration of traditional control systems, such as programmable logic controllers with advanced artificial intelligence technologies. This synergy represents a key step towards the formation of intelligent production systems capable of independently analyzing, predicting and optimizing processes in real time. During the work, it was shown that PLC, as a basic element of automation, ensures stability, accuracy and reliability in the management of industrial processes, while AI introduces the dimension of adaptive learning and predictive decision-making. The combination of these technologies achieves a significant increase in efficiency, quality and flexibility of production, while reducing costs and downtime. The results of the analysis show that the integration of PLC and AI systems brings numerous advantages – increasing productivity, predictive maintenance, energy optimization and reducing human intervention. However, numerous challenges of limitation of the processing power of PLC devices, the need for standardization of

communication protocols, security risks and lack of professional staff were also observed. The research results indicate that the application of AI technologies will redefine the automation process from traditional PLC systems to more intelligent and adaptive solutions. The future of industrial automation is based on the tight integration of PLC and AI technologies, as well as the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) and PLC programming, whereby the PLC will retain the role of a stable control core, while AI will represent the brain of the system that enables decision-making based on data analysis and experience.

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